

DISCUS PROJECT 21470018

RESEARCH STUDY

RECOMMENDATIONS ON ACTION PLAN FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF LOCAL E-SERVICES

**NOVEMBER - DECEMBER
2015**

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Recommendations on action plan for implementation of local e-services

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Table of contents

Table of contents	3
1. Introduction	5
2. The impact of the seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (Practical Issues).....	5
3. Important issues identified in building ICT based local services in Moldova	7
3.1. Personal Data Protection	7
3.1.1. Basic notions.....	7
3.1.2. The responsibilities of personal data subject	8
3.2. Use of “.md” National Domain and Data security	9
3.3. Use of e-Government platform.....	13
3.4. Use of Common Applications	14
3.5. Use of Financial opportunities	15
3.5.1.AMP Platform	16
3.5.2. Cross-border cooperation at the external borders of the EU	16
3.5.3. Joint Operational Programme Romania-Republic of Moldova 2014-2020	17
3.5.4. Top Donors by Commitments.....	18
3.5.3. Donors profiles and normative framework.....	19
4. Levels of e-Services.....	21
5. Pre-conditions before writing Action Plan for e-Services	21
5.1. Introduction and the State of the Art Chapter	21
5.2. Local Legal Framework.....	22
5.3. SWOT Analysis of the LPA.....	22
5.4. Competences	23
5.5. Data	23
5.6. Needs	24
5.7. Infrastructure and Technologies.....	24
5.8. Personal Resources.....	25
6. Action Plan for e-Services development / implementation.....	26
7. Questionnaire for LPA from the Republic of Moldova	29
Conclusions & Recommendations.....	32
Bibliography.....	33
Annex 1. Seminar Agenda of the seminar.....	34
Annex 2: The 7th project factsheet – Seminar from November 24-25, 2015 ...	36
Annex 3. Personal data categories.....	37

Abbreviations

DISCUS – Discussion on Information Society Building Issues Platform

ISDI/IDSI – Information Society Development Institute, Moldova

V4 – Visegrad countries

ICT – Information & Communication Technologies

ISPA - Information System of the Public Administration

CMS – Content Management System

LPA – Local Public Authorities

IDNO – Juridical Person Identification Number

IDNP – Physical Person Identification Number

RM – Republic of Moldova

UNDP – United Nations Development Program

ITIL – Information Technology Infrastructure Library

ISO – International Organization for Standardization

TOGAF – The Open Group Architecture Framework

WGAG – Web Content Accessibility Guidelines

IEC – International Electrotechnical Commission

ESC – European Committee for Standardization

ETSI – European Telecommunications Standards Institute

1. Introduction

The Report for the fourth DISCUS event – seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (Practical Issues) held on November 24-25, 2015 in Chisinau, Moldova shall be based on:

- Approved DISCUS Project Document,
- TOR provisions,
- Own experience on best practices in Visegrad countries in ICT solutions for local services (with focus on planning and strategic aspects),
- Analyzed V4/EU countries experience/initiatives relevant to the DISCUS project objectives,
- Analysis of presented information and discussions during the seminar,
- Analysis of issues, solutions, plans proposed by the local authorities representatives and other stakeholders expressed during the event,
- Analysis of ideas expressed during informal communication at the seminar;
- Analysis of the evaluation questionnaires completed by participants at the end of the event.

The research study “**Recommendations on action plan for implementation of local e-services**” is written within the DISCUS project as the result of the seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (Practical Issues).

The main goal of this research study is to present the results of the seminar from November on ICT Solutions for Local Services (Practical Issues). Firstly is made a short analysis of the event and the impact of the DISCUS seminar is presented. An analysis of the actual relevant problems identified during the seminar was performed: personal data protection; use of national domain .md; financial opportunities for LPAs from Moldova. Following the general notions on e-services, the levels of e-service are presented. There pre-conditions before writing action plan for e-services are specified, which should be taken into consideration by the LPA. For a better understanding, a set of complex analyses are presented: SWOT; Data, Competencies, Needs, Infrastructure and IT analysis. There is a special chapter dedicated to the Action Plan for e-services development, which describes what an action plan is, how it looks and is given a general template of the action plan for e-service implementation. Within the research study, there is a questionnaire for LPAs from the Republic of Moldova, proposed by the Visegrad and Moldovan experts, based on the findings of the seminar (as well as all project events during 2015).

2. The impact of the seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (Practical Issues)

The seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (Practical Issues) took place on November 24-25, in Chisinau. The event was attended by **120 participants**, including 15 mayors, 20 deputy mayors, secretaries of local/district councils, 20 representatives of libraries, schools/colleges/universities, as well as several specialists from local public authorities of Ist and IInd level from Moldova. Also at the event have participated representatives of academic sector, central government, civil society, national experts and international experts from Visegrad countries. The event was online streamed; approx. **250 users** had visualized the video.

The project was assessed positively by the government representatives and Academy of Sciences management. The event was attended by Acad. Ion Tighineanu, senior vice president of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova; Sergiu Ceaus, Deputy Secretary General of the Government; Andrei Cusca, Ministry of Information Technology and Communications; Dr. Veaceslav Ursachi, head of the Engineering and Technology Sciences Department of ASM. According to evaluation questionnaires full filled by participants at the event, they appreciated the presence and presentations of the government representatives and Academy of Sciences of Moldova. Their messages have conferred more trust to all participants that all stakeholders of the information society development process are interested and take into account the local problems. In a way, this was a message of encouraging for mayors, local specialists that they are supported by the central decision makers.

The **main goal** of the event was to approach the problem of the local e-services from the practical point of view.

The **objective of the seminar** was to inform and raise awareness among moldovan local public servants as well as different stakeholders regarding the information society development process, with an accent on the need to develop and implement e-services at the local level. Also, to present different aspects of the local electronic services by several development partners, government representatives, central authorities, academia vision. During the seminar, the local representatives could express their problems and visions how they can solve these problems with the help of the new information technology. National and Visegrad experts consulted and advised representatives of LPAs. Visegrad experts presented some of the best practices of their countries, as models that can inspire the Moldavian servants, both of the central and local level.

The seminar started with the presentation of practical issues regarding the protection of personal data, carried out by two experts from the National Center for Personal Data Protection. This subject was practically new for LPAs, even they had the legal duty to register the authority as holder of personal data. Based on the final evaluation questionnaire, this subject was appreciated by the participants as one of the most useful, presented during the event.

The representatives of the State Chancellery presented the funding instruments from external sources for LPAs. Therefore, the local servants could find out several external funds that can finance their projects.

Experts from e-Government Center demonstrated reusable electronic government services. There was presented the national e-service portal: www.servicii.gov.md, and the e-services that can be reused at the local level. Once again was shown what have been done until now at the central level and what can teach local administration from this experience.

Because during first 3 events of the DISCUS project organized in Chisinau, one of the problems of the IT at local level was identified and discussed was the web pages of the LPAs done on foreign domain. In this propose, was invited the administrator of SE MoldData - Dorian Bodiu. He spoke about the ".MD" domain for LPAs: penetrability, challenges and reality. Were discussed the issues of local authorities with the development of web pages, maintenance of official emails, cyber security.

Project manager and IT consultant for UNDP – Olesea Cazau and Eugen Platitu presented IT instruments for LPAs, developed within the projects implemented by UNDP Moldova. They announced about the Document Management IT system development as a tool for LPAs from Moldova. Novateca program results were presented and were announced the next activities within the

program as opportunities for local, rural libraries as well as for LPAs that manage with local libraries; including IT opportunities.

Experts from the Visegrad countries: Poland, Slovakia, the Czech Republic came up with several suggestions for implementation of e-services at the local level, by sharing the experiences from their respective countries. Participants had opportunities, during the event, to ask questions about Visegrad experience especially in rural areas.

A topic of interest for local government representatives was the presentation focused on "Household Register. Conceptual Approach" delivered by Mihai Grecu - Information Society Development Institute. Even until now have been started a lot of initiatives at central level to find a IT solution for this problem, today there is no concrete result and LPAs continue to issue and keep a lot of documents on papers.

ISDI Director, Dr. Igor Cojocaru presented innovative services of ISDI, which could be opportunities for LPAs, services like virtual tour, network management, information systems development, web development etc.

According to the evaluation questionnaires, the participant's expectations were met and they appreciated that had the opportunity to express their opinions concerning local problems and to propose some plan how can be solved with IT. It means that LPAs need periodical dialog with different stakeholders: government representatives, academia sector, civil society and so on. In this respect, during 2015 DISCUS became an efficient Discussion on Information Society Development Issues Platform. Starting from events of 50 – 60 participants (in March 2015) DISCUS platform could gather more than 120 representatives of different sectors: government, LPAs, academia, civil society, media; in November 2015. During the DISCUS events, the participants from 33 districts from the Republic of Moldova mentioned that DISCUS should be a permanent platform of communication where all interested parts could meet regularly and discuss problems vs (IT) solutions for public services (with an accent on local level). It has become a common "place" where all development partners can put on agenda their ideas, proposals and plans.

3. Important issues identified in building ICT based local services in Moldova

3.1. Personal Data Protection

3.1.1. Basic notions

personal data - any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (such as name, phone number, email address, data and place of birth etc.);

special categories of personal data – data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, social belonging, data concerning health or sex life, as well as data relating to criminal convictions, administrative sanctions or coercive procedural measures;

processing of personal data – any operation or set of operations which is performed upon personal data, whether or not by automatic means, such as collection, recording, organization, storage, keeping, restoring, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, combination, blocking, erasure or destruction;

controller – a natural or legal person governed by public law, or by private law, including public authority, agency or any other body which alone or jointly with others determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data expressly provided by applicable law;

processor – a natural or legal person governed by public law, or by private law, including public authority and its territorial subdivisions, which processes personal data on behalf of the controller, on instructions from the controller.

3.1.2. The responsibilities of personal data subject

1. Contraventional liability:

The National Center for Personal Data Protection is the institution responsible for data protection in Moldova. The center is entitled to find contraventions, referred to in Article 741-743 of the Contravention Code and to draw up reports on contraventions, which are later sent for examination to a competent court.

Some contraventions found by the National Center for Personal Data Protection:

- Failure to comply with requirements for ensuring the security of personal data processing within the personal data information systems;
- Processing of personal data without notice and / or authorization from the controlling body in the processing of personal data;
- Violations of the personal data subject's rights to be informed, to access his personal data and modify the personal data, to oppose and not be the subject of an individual decisions;
- Refusal to provide information or preventing access of the staff of the National Center for Personal Data Protection etc.
- Penalties – a fine of 300 c.u. for individual officials, 500 c.u. for a legal entity, with or without deprivation, in all cases, of the right to carry out certain activities for a period from 3 months to one year.

2. Civil liability

Following a lawsuit, the controller/processor could be ordered to compensate the moral/material damage of a subject, whose rights were violated, by not complying to personal data protection processing legislation (the Eriomenco case in 2014, when the Supreme Court ordered the Ministry of Internal Affairs the acquittal of a moral injury of 200,000 lei).

3. Criminal liability

This liability may arise in certain circumstances, such as significant damage etc. For ex. Art. 261 of the Criminal Code "Violation of information system security rules" provides for sentences of up to 400 conventional units or community service for 200 to 240 hours or imprisonment for up to 2 years in all cases with (or without) the deprivation of the right to occupy certain positions or to practice certain activities for a period of 2 to 5 years, a legal entity shall be punished by a fine of 1000 to 3000 conventional units with the deprivation of the right to perform certain activities.

Notification requirement

According to art. 23 of the Law on personal data protection, all personal data controllers must notify the Center on processing of personal data intended to serve a purpose and provide the Centre

with information regarding the implementation of an institutional security policy, as required for ensuring the security of personal data during their processing within personal data information systems, approved by Government Decision nr. 1123 of 14 December 2010.

The procedures for notification and registration are performed by the personal data controller or processor, for each personal data filing system, via an application available on the web page www.registru.datepersonale.md, according to Art. 23-28 of the Law on personal data protection and the Regulation of the register of personal data controllers, approved by Government Decision nr. 296 of 15 May 2012.

Ensuring adequate security level

Personal data protection within information systems is to be achieved through the following ways:

The principle of "Privacy by design" – it is appropriate that the principles of confidentiality and personal data protection are to be incorporated into the technology life cycle, from the early design stage to the deployment, use and its deletion from information systems.

Such a mechanism would greatly benefit the individual person concerned, because it would benefit from protection without initiating it. This aspect is particularly important in a context, when many of the personal data are processed without the knowledge and/or consent of the subject.

In addition, the entity implementing such a mechanism, will get several benefits such as minimizing risks, high level of transparency and trust from the individual person, much lower volume of initial investment in personal data protection, than the subsequent management of potential security incidents and payment of moral damages etc.

More information is available at <http://www.registru.datepersonale.md>

Conclusions:

Personal data processing requires a specific approach, that needs to be acknowledged and requires special measures. Increased use of ICTs in LPA leads to an increased risk of violation of citizens' rights related to personal data processing, therefore LPA must be registered as personal data controllers with the National Center for Personal Data Protection.

3.2. Use of “.md” National Domain and Data security

The top-level domain .md is the code of the Republic of Moldova attributed by the Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers (ICANN), in compliance with the ISO–3166 international standard, as a top-level domain name for the identification of the country in the Internet. The Law on Electronic Communications no. 241-XVI of 15.11.2007 establishes one of ANRCETI functions: to develop regulations on top-level domain.md management. The above-mentioned Law provides for the top-level domain .md being state property, which cannot be subject to sale, purchase or lease.

The sub-domains of the top-level domain .md are registered, re-registered and sold according to the Regulations on Name Administration in the Top-level Domain.md, approved by ANRCETI. The Regulations sets forth the main rules and principles of administration of top-level domain .md names, determines the authorities responsible for the policy, strategy and management of such names, their functions and responsibilities, including the ones of the National Registrar of top-level domain

.md names, procedures of registration, extension, modification or cancellation of names from the sub-domain registers within the top-level domain .md.

The new version of the Regulations establishes, inter alia, the obligation of the registrant to verify the veracity of the data included in the registration form, some of the restrictions related to the act of displaying on sub-domain sites obscene or offensive information, or information aspersing the image of Moldova or other countries, call to violence or may defame the image of the Republic of Moldova on international level, as well as links to sites containing such information.¹

The National Registrar authority responsible for the administration of names in the top-level domain .md is an enterprise, located in the Republic of Moldova, acting in the area of Informatics, appointed by the Ministry. This role is performed by the State Enterprise Molddata.

Annex II to **Regulations on the management of top-level domain .md names**, sets a list of Geographical sub-domain names assigned to local public administration bodies, where registration is carried out free of charge.

Domain name	Locality.md	Domain name	Locality.md
1. an.md	Aneni	25. co.md	Comrat
2. cs.md	Causeni	26. ch.md	Cahul
3. bn.md	Bender	27. cci.md	Ciocana (Chisinau)
4. cg.md	Ceadir Lunga	28. cr.md	Criuleni
5. bl.md	Balti	29. ct.md	Cantemir
6. cce.md	Centru (Chishinau)	30. cbu.md	Buicani (Chisinau)
7. bs.md	Basarabesca	31. dn.md	Donduseni
8. chn.md	Chisinau	32. cn.md	Cainari
9. cbo.md	Botanica (Chisinau)	33. dr.md	Drochia
10. cm.md	Cimislia	34. sv.md	Stefan Voda
11. gr.md	Grigoriopol	35. tr.md	Taraclia
12. hn.md	Hincesti	36. ti.md	Tighina
13. il.md	Ialoveni	37. ts.md	Tiraspol
14. lp.md	Lăpuşna	38. tl.md	Telenesti
15. lv.md	Leova	39. un.md	Ungheni
16. ns.md	Nisporeni	40. vl.md	Vulcanesti
17. oc.md	Ocnita	41. ugi.md	Gagauzia
18. or.md	Orhei	42. cl.md	Calarasi
19. rz.md	Rezina	43. db.md	Dubasari
20. rb.md	Ribnita	44. ed.md	Edinet
21. rs.md	Riscani	45. fl.md	Falesti
22. sg.md	Singerei	46. fr.md	Floresti
23. sl.md	Slobozia	47. gl.md	Glodeni
24. br..md	Briceni	48. sr.md	Soroca

These subdomains are not used for commercial purposes.²

¹ <http://www.anrceti.md/node/35>

² [Anexa 2 al Regulamentului modificată prin Hot.ANRTI nr.21 din 30.12.05, în vigoare 13.01.06]

According to data provided by Molddata, the statistics on domain names .md in November 2015 is as follows:

The "dot MD" (.MD) Domain:

TOTAL: 24 897 records (domain names)

-837 Names of localities

-316 Designation of public authorities and institutions and their projects.

The use of the .md domain by the local public authorities is presented in the table below.

Table 1. Use of .md domain by local authorities

ATU level II/ATU/municipality	Corresponding domain name	Active mail service ".MD" zone
Chişinău municipality	chisinau.md	yes
Bălţi municipality	balti.md	Yes
Bender municipality	bendery-ga.org ?	No
ATU Găgăuzia	gagauzia.md	Yes
Anenii-Noi district	anenii-noi.md	Yes
Basarabeasca district	basarabeasca.moldova.md	No
Briceni district	br.md	Yes
Cahul district	cahul.md	Yes
Cantemir district	cantemir.md	Yes
Călăraşi district	calarasi.md	Yes
Căuşeni district	causeni.md	Yes
Cimişlia district	raioncimislia.md	Yes
Criuleni district	criuleni.md	Yes
Donuşeni district	donduseni.md	No
Drochia district	drochia.md	Yes
Dubasari district	dubasari.md	No
Edineţ district	edinet.md	Yes
Făleşti district	cr-falesti.md	Yes
Floreşti district	-	-
Glodeni district	glodeni.md	yes?----mail.md
Hînceşti district	hincesti.md	Yes
Ialoveni district	il.md	Yes
Leova district	leova.md	Yes
Nisporeni district	nisporeni.md	yes?----mail.ru
Ocnîţa district	ocnita.md	Yes
Orhei district	orhei.moldova.md?	-
Rezina district	consiliu.rezina.md	Yes
Rîşcani district	riscani.md	Yes
Sîngerei district	singerei.md	yes?---yahoo.com
Soroca district	soroca.org.md	Yes
Străşeni district	crstraseni.md	yes?---gmail.com

Șoldănești district	soldanesti.md	Yes
Ștefan-Vodă district	stefan-voda.md	Yes
Taraclia district	-	-
Telenești district	telenesti.md	Yes
Ungheni district	crungheni.md	yes?---mtc-un.md

According to the study on the web presence of localities in Moldova, carried out by the Information Society Development Institute in April 2014, 425 localities out of the 1525 have been identified on the Internet or 28% of the total. The other 1,098 places haven't been identified on the web.

Out of the 425 localities with a web presence, 193 own a web page on the website of other institutions, most of them on the website of the municipal district councils. Other 38% of localities have a website and 60 communities have a blog.

Below is illustrated the internet presence of localities in Moldova according to districts (eastern districts of Moldova were not included in the study):

Fig. 1 Web presence of localities in Moldova

It should be noted that only 80 localities use the domain name .md, or 19% of the total. Most institutions (70 localities or 16%) use blogging platforms, that are offered for free (fig. 2).

Fig 2. Domain names used by web pages of localities from Moldova

The conclusion is that local public authorities do not benefit from the provisions of the **Regulations on Name Administration in the Top-level Domain.md** on one hand and on the other hand use other countries domains, which leads to increased information security risks (information is stored on foreign servers).

3.3. Use of e-Government platform

Web Based Technology. The solutions initiated by JILD P at the local level are based on web technology, allowing the client to be independent of its geographical location. This system tends to bring together all parties involved in recording Moldovan touristic heritage in a single collaboration platform.

Integration with Governmental Infrastructure. Interoperability.

Interoperability is ensured through government interoperability platform "MConnect", through use of web services.

For all external IS which allow for XML-based electronic data exchange, interoperability is achieved through web services, using standard protocols such as XML, SOAP, HTTPS and others.

Interoperability Platform "MConnect" supports IT solutions, by reducing the number of connections to other information resources involved in the proper functioning of the system. Interoperability platform represents a national data bus, that interconnects many data suppliers/users.

Platform services

To ensure the correct composition of the aforesaid information resources, access to the following information resources of the platform services is offered:

MPass authentication service to authenticate users in the system;

MSign - digital signature;

MLog - journaling service to ensure the system audit.

It is highly advisable to reuse at the local level the instruments that have already been developed.

3.4. Use of Common Applications

Official Internet pages of public authorities in Moldova

In order to meet the provisions of the Government Decision nr. 188 of 03.04.2012 on the official pages of public administration authorities on the Internet, Special Telecommunications Center provides a platform hosting official websites, developed using the unique template provided by e-Government Center.

The unique template of websites of public administration aims to guarantee the quality and usefulness of these web sites, covering the following main objectives:

- user/citizen oriented;
- simple and efficient navigation, keeping the same feeling of the information/virtual space on any government websites;
- maximum utility;
- increased transparency of the AAP and access to public information;
- unified graphic style, that reflects state membership and meets the status of public authority.

The citizens will have the opportunity, through official websites, to interact with public authorities, participating in online discussion forums and online conferences.

According to the Regulation, an official web page shall operate non-stop. Time to suspend its operation for the planned technical service, shall not exceed three hours per month. Websites will be adapted to be accessed from any mobile phone and smartphone. Access to official websites will be free and open, as before, only now authorities reserve the right to provide public services against payment via their official websites.

Meanwhile, official websites should provide a subscription option to citizens, to the information from the news, events and announcements blocks. Official web page content will be delivered to the public in three languages.

The Government is committed to ensuring the protection and security of information through qualified individuals with expertise in information security and regulatory-legal framework in Moldova.

The regulation on official websites of public administration authorities on the Internet was developed in order to enhance the level of transparency of public authorities and access to public information through the Internet.

Joint Integrated Local Development Program

Since 2009 the Government of the Republic of Moldova (State Chancellery), in partnership with United Nations Development Program and United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment, have been implementing the Joint Integrated Local Development Program (JILDLP) funded by the Government of Sweden. In 2013 the Government of Denmark adhered to the program, by offering funds for the local development component of the second phase of JILDLP.

JILDIP was designed to improve the policy framework and to support administrative systems and procedures, focused on efficient transfer of competencies to local public authorities (LPA), decentralization and promotion of LPA role in decision-making etc. The program also contributes to LPA capacity building in planning, implementing and monitoring their strategic plans, as well as to improved local public services, involving civil society and encouraging efforts and greater community participation.

Regardless of the organizational model of the LPA (service-oriented or classical), software services and web technologies development provide a way to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of large bureaucratic organizations.

Therefore such terms as e-Commerce, e-Government, e-Organization, e-Participation etc. have become increasingly more used.

The project has identified several examples services required at the local level:

- Income tax collection services for the citizens
- Services for tracking social assistance benefits
- Requiring various conformity certificates issued by LPAs
- Payment and monitoring of contributions to the local budget
- Utilities recording
- The issuance of operating and building permits
- Enrollment of children in kindergartens and schools
- Job search
- Statistical data of economic agents etc.

The first e-steps at the local level, initiated by UNDP/JILDIP:

- Integrated Document Management System for Local Public Authorities
- "e-Learning" platform for local officials
- System for public consultation through SMS polls
- Utilities recording
- Internet access
- Monitoring vehicles through GPS and other

Implementation of these projects will contribute to promoting the image of Moldova regarding innovative approaches, creating a more comfortable infrastructure at the local level, thus making rural areas more attractive for investment.

3.5. Use of Financial opportunities

The State Chancellery (SC) is the Central Public Administration (CPA) body that has the overall responsibility for PAR in terms of strategic planning, policy and donor coordination, monitoring and evaluation. SC is responsible over the regulatory framework related to administrative normative acts, legal status of civil servants, coordination of the decentralisation

Strategy, e-Transformation agenda (through its e-Government Centre), cross border cooperation initiatives (including participation in Danube Transnational Programme) and coordination of public service modernisation National Programme.

3.5.1.AMP Platform

The special platform was created to help to access the foreign financial assistance www.amp.gov.md. The Foreign Aid Management Platform (AMP) - represents an on-line data management platform of external assistance or projects, programs and other forms of assistance provided by development partners.

Through AMP platform the users can follow:

- All external assistance projects that have been completed, planned and ongoing, having necessary information about the objectives, actions, duration and budget of the project;
- Annual reports on foreign assistance;
- Donor's profiles and normative framework;
- View the Map of Moldova areas / localities where it conducts foreign assistance

External assistance projects that are in line with national development priorities of the Government are coordinated directly with external partners (donors) and Central Public Administration (Government).

But Cross-border Cooperation Programmes can be coordinated / implemented directly by local government and the European Union. To obtain the financing one has to follow strictly Donor rules, which obviously are published.

3.5.2. Cross-border cooperation at the external borders of the EU

The strategic objectives of the European Neighborhood Instrument (ENI) 2014-2020:

- Promoting social and economic development of regions on both sides of the border
- Troubleshooting common environmental, public health, safety and security
- Promoting better conditions for ensuring the mobility of people, goods and capital

Funding conditions:

- Projects must ensure a clear cross-border impact and added value for EU strategies and programs;
- Projects are implemented in the program area
- Not accepted duplication of financing the same actions in different EU sources
- Not accepted retroactive financing of projects.

The partnership principle

- Projects are based on cross-border partnerships between Member States and partner / candidate (Turkey);
- Each project appoint a leader to represent the partnership contract with the donor, represented by MA (is signing the financing contract);
- All partners must work actively in the development and implementation of projects and must provide personal and / or co-financing, under a partnership agreement signing it;

- Project leader receives funding from the MA and provides transfer the project to partners, according to the Partnership;
- The leader takes responsibility for the entire project implementation;
- Each partner is legally and financially responsible for the activities they implement and manage the grant it receives.

2014 – 2020 Bilateral programs successor PO ROUAMD:

1. Programme Romania-Moldova
2. Programme Romania-Ukraine
3. Black Sea Basin Joint Operational Programme

3.5.3. Joint Operational Programme Romania-Republic of Moldova 2014-2020

The program area:

The counties of Botosani, Iasi, Vaslui, Galati

The entire territory of the Republic of Moldova

Allocations: 81 million euros (ENI funds)

The minimum co-financing to ensure the two countries is 10% of the EU contribution.

Eligible projects:

Funded projects Ro-Ua-Md must fall into one of these categories:

- Integrated projects, where each partner realizes different activities on its own side of the border in order to achieve a common objective, cross-border impact;
- Symmetrical projects where similar activities are carried out in parallel Embark on border states;
- Simple projects implemented mainly or entirely in one partner country in the program but which have an impact across borders.

ELIGIBLE - potential beneficiaries can receive funding under the program, by priority and measure.

Priority 1: Towards a more competitive economy of the border area

1.1 Improving the productivity and competitiveness of urban and rural areas:

chamber of commerce, local and regional authorities, universities, other educational institutions such as business colleges, public institutions supporting the work force (job creation centers employment services employment exchanges etc.), NGOs and professional and business associations legally established public institutions responsible for promoting tourism, local associations of municipalities and municipal administrations.

1.2 Development of cooperation initiatives in transport, border infrastructure and energy networks.

Local and regional authorities, public sector entities operating in transport (railways and roads), public entities in the energy sector and public service providers, bodies responsible for border crossing management.

Priority 2: Environment and preparedness for emergency situations

2.1 Addressing the environmental issues, including preparing for emergencies.

Local and regional authorities, environmental agencies and agencies involved in water management and flood protection, nongovernmental organizations, administrations of national parks and protected natural areas, universities and other institutions of higher education inspectorates for emergencies, other legal bodies involved in the development of emergency plans.

2.2 Management of water resources and waste.

Local and regional organizations involved in waste management at county and regional public bodies regional and county waste water management, NGOs, non-profit organizations;

Information on ongoing projects can be found on

[//">http://amp.gov.md/viewTeamReports.do?tabs=false&language=en //](http://amp.gov.md/viewTeamReports.do?tabs=false&language=en)

<http://amp.gov.md/aim/viewNewAdvancedReport.do~view=reset&widget=false&resetSettings=true~ampReportId=1033>

3.5.4. Top Donors by Commitments

Donor Agency	Actual Commitments (EUR)
European Commission	65,900,421.4
International Development Agency	10,810,810.81
United States of America	7,699,178.45
Republic of Austria	6,005,100
Denmark	4,699,063.75
The Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria	2,772,080
European Union	2,750,184.56
US Department Of Defense	925,014.01
United States Department Of State	707,265.55
Food and Agriculture Organization	605,614.21

3.5.3. Donors profiles and normative framework

Donors profiles and normative framework can be found at:

<http://www.amp.gov.md/portal/organizations?language=en>

Following the link further you can access the profile of any listed donor, for example Estonia <http://www.amp.gov.md/portal/node/20?language=en> and its profile will be displayed with all available information on financing and assistance priorities and procedures. Although there are many similarities, each donor has own rules, that donor is publishing on their websites.

Accessing the link **View the profile of this donor in a dashboard** you will be guided to deeper information on assistance sectors, aid amounts of money and other information.

View the profile of this donor in a dashboard	
Development partner	Estonia
Development/ Implementation agency	<p>The Ministry of Foreign Affairs is responsible for the strategic planning, implementation and coordinating the activities of different participants of Estonian development cooperation.</p> <p>Other ministries are primarily responsible for planning, implementing and evaluating development cooperation projects in their own field and for development of direct relationships with relevant institutions in developing countries, keeping in mind the goals of this Strategy.</p>
Contact details	<p>Estonia covers Moldova from the Estonian Embassy in Kiev 43B Pushkinskaya street, Kiev 01901, Ukraine Tel. +380 44 590 0780 Fax. +380 44 590 0781 Email: Embassy.Kyiv@mfa.ee Website: http://www.vm.ee/?q=en/node/74 and www.estemb.kiev.ua</p>
Legal framework for cooperation	<p>Co-operation Protocol between the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Estonia and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Moldova (came into force on 03.04.1996).</p> <p>The Government of the Republic of Estonia regulation “Conditions of and Procedures for Provision of Development and Humanitarian Aid” (entered into force on 15 February 2010).</p>
Strategic documents for programming	<p>Strategy For Estonian Development Cooperation And Humanitarian Aid 2011–2015. The overall goal of Estonian development cooperation is to contribute to the eradication of world poverty and to attaining the Millennium Development Goals.</p> <p>Moldova is one of the priority partner countries for Estonia since 2006.</p>

<p>Priority sectors/ Areas of cooperation</p>	<p>Year EUR 2012 – 487,000 (disbursed) 2013 – 500,000 (planned) 2014 – 700,000 (tentative) 2015 – 900,000 (tentative) Priority sectors: • Health sector • Education/ science • Good governance/ justice • Economic development • Other</p>
<p>Types of funds / financial instruments and assistance modalities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical assistance/Training • Grants/Scholarships
<p>Procedures for programming, approval and implementation of projects</p>	<p>The projects are identified by the Estonian side.</p> <p>As of 2000 Estonia’s contribution to various projects has increased tenfold. In addition to its co-operation with the Foreign Ministry, successful co-operation with Moldova has also taken place through other Estonian ministries and institutions (Ministry of Social Affairs, Ministry of the Interior, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of the Environment, Ministry of Education and Research, the National Audit Office, Academy of Security Sciences, and the Border Guard Board).</p> <p>The non-governmental sector is also showing increased interest in working in and with Moldova.</p> <p>Representatives of ministries and civil associations participate in the development cooperation project evaluation committee that approves bilateral development cooperation projects and supervises their implementation.</p>
<p>Other information</p>	<p>Eastern Partnership (EaP) Training Centre</p> <p>Since the beginning of 2011 the EU Eastern Partnership Training Centre started to operate in Tallinn. Based on current experiences of Estonian School of Diplomacy, training centre carries out training programmes and seminars related to various aspects of public administration reform to the EaP countries, including Moldova. The Centre is funded from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs development co-operation budget.</p>

4. Levels of e-Services

What is electronic Service (e-Service)?

Wikipedia: ‘The **online services** available **on the Internet**, whereby a valid transaction of buying and selling (procurement) is possible, as opposed to the traditional **websites**, whereby **only descriptive information** are available and no online transaction is made possible.’

When we are speaking about e-Services in public sector, the above definition could serve as parallel.

Levels of e-Services:

- **Level 0** – provider **without on-line access or without web**, client is using **paper form**
- **Level 1 (informative)** – provider’s **web with basic information** for client, e.g. contacts, working hours, documents and others to start
- **Level 2 (transaction – 1-way interaction)** - provider’s **web with forms** for client for download. **Client is filling data offline** + completed annexes, **sending** by mail or personally to provider. Decision of provider delivered to client by mail or personally by client’s visit.
- **Level 3 (transaction – duplex interaction)** - provider’s **web with forms** for client, who can use it for **sending through web after offline filling**. Needed authentication of client. Decision of provider delivered to client by mail or personally by client’s visit. Information about state of the admin process ready for client.
- **Level 4 (transaction)** - provider’s **web with e-Service** for client for **online filling and sending** to provider, including financial transaction. Information about state of the admin process ready for client. Needed authentication of client. No other personal or mail contacts needed.
- **Level 5 (personalized - automated)** – **proactive approach by on-line e-Service** offering personalized content. Based on social or economic client’s profile there are offered automated e-Services **without direct client’s impulse**.

5. Pre-conditions before writing Action Plan for e-Services

Thinking on own LPA situation from various aspects is crucial for preparation of good Action Plan for development of electronic Services (e-Services). This section will help you to propose e-Services, which are realistic and efficient to develop in your conditions and will help to organize work to improve these pre-conditions.

For the beginning is very important to understand what was done before and to analyze actual circumstances.

5.1. Introduction and the State of the Art Chapter

The "**state of the art**" chapter refers to the highest level of general development, achieved at a particular time, in this case – the current situation. Introduction and the state of the art should answer to the questions concerning general data (surface of the locality, the region, the general development level, and socio-economic data). Besides this general information and statistic

indicators, the chapter should include a general analyze of development of the IT field, a short description of what have been done until now. The chapter should end with 2-3 main conclusions.

5.2. Local Legal Framework

This point should include a short analysis of the local regulations in terms of IT and e-services. For example, if there are any local medium or long term development strategies, if this strategy stipulates any clauses concerning IT. Here might be listed all local documents, decisions which focus on IT, e-infrastructure, any equipment, IT specialists/HR (employment, redundancies, trainings, study visits, projects etc.) or other related topics.

Table 1: Legal framework

Document/ Public decision title:	No. /date	Subject (short)	IT component

5.3. SWOT Analysis of the LPA

A SWOT analysis (alternatively SWOT matrix) is a structured planning method used to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats involved in an authority. SWOT analysis aims to identify the key internal and external factors seen as important to achieving an objective. SWOT analysis groups key pieces of information into two main categories:

1. **Internal factors** – the strengths and weaknesses internal to the authority:
 - Human resources
 - Finances
 - Internal advantages/disadvantages of the authority
 - Physical resources
 - Experiences including what has worked or has not worked in the past

2. **External factors** – the opportunities and threats presented by the environment external to the authority:
 - Trends (new research)
 - Society’s cultural, political, and economic ideology
 - Funding sources
 - Current events
 - Societal oppression

Table 2: SWOT Analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
1. 2.	
Opportunities	Threats

5.4. Competences

Name here all your competences according to law and try to propose where you can see possibility to develop eServices.

Table 3: Competences

Competence:	Based on legal act:	Nr.of eService:	Possible eService:

Summary to this section:

We need to do:

1. ...

5.5. Data

Identify the state of data in your LPA which can be used for eServices. Remember that only timely, valid and reliable data can be used in eServices. Think on data you can use for eServices in the following manners:

- Own data
- National data and level of access

Table 4: Data

Type of data:	Source of data (own or other):	Quality of data:	Need for eService No.: (use No.from table 1)

When planning eServices, also take into account the accessibility of existing eServices.

- Own Services which can be used
- National Services which can be used

Table 5: Accessibility to existing eServices

Name of eService:	Level of eService (0-5):	Operator of eService:	Usage of eService with planned own eService No.: (use No. from table 1)

Summary to this section:

We need to do:

1. ...

5.6. Needs

Describe here your knowledge about the clients' needs/requirements for eServices. Take into account also your own needs/requirements and the needs/requirements of other public authorities (PA).

Table 6:

nr:	Name of eService:	Target users: Citizens / Entrepreneurs / NGOs / my PA / other PAs	Status of eService: (in operation / planned / ...)	Operator of eService:

Summary to this section:

We need to do:

1. ...

5.7. Infrastructure and Technologies

When building eServices it is important to have good data organization and secure access provided to these. For communication with clients, it is important to have the possibility to clearly identify the client and to have Document Management System applied in your LPA. As basic information for this section could serve the questionnaire for Local Public Authorities (please see chapter 6).

Please answer the following questions related to data organization:

- Where are your data stored?
- Do you have solved security of data?
- Did you apply a system of classifiers and identifiers for you data?
- Did you use standards? Which one? Based on which legal act?

Please answer the following questions related to clients' access:

- What type of clients' identification do you use? (electronic ID card / login & password & authorization by GRID card or SMS, ...)
- Try to assess the percentage of clients depending on identification to your systems (from No identification to eIS card)
- Do you have clients' electronic signature applied? Which type?

Summary to this section:

We need to do:

1. ...

5.8. Personal Resources

Identify here the personal staff important for development and operation of eServices. Use the table below and put the names of persons responsible for eServices development / implementation, IT specialists, persons responsible for separate agendas and so on.

Table 5: Personal Resources

Name of person:	Internal / External:	Role:	Relation to eService No.:

Summary to this section:

We need to do:

1. ...

6. Action Plan for e-Services development / implementation

An action plan³ consists of a number of action steps or changes to be brought about in your community.

Each action step or change to be sought should include the following information:

- **What** actions or changes will occur – concrete actions, described shortly and clearly
- **Who** will carry out these changes – responsible for each action/sub action
- **By when** they will take place, and for how long – a concrete deadline settled (day, month, year where it is possible or trimester)
- **What resources** (i.e., money, staff) are needed to carry out these changes – both internal and external needed resources
- **Communication** (who should know what?) - a communication scheme can be approved by the team, including communication tools and terms

Before starting of Action Plan writing, sort please summaries from above sections and write firstly the common tasks (common which need to be solved/implemented before building of individual e-Services) and set priorities to them.

Action Plan of common tasks as basis for building e-Services

....

Based on common tasks identification try to guess expenditures and comparing with financial possibilities decide about further continuation.

Estimation of expenditures for Action Plan of common tasks:

Possible finances:

³ What is an action plan? <http://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/structure/strategic-planning/develop-action-plans/main>

Copy this table separately for each proposed eService.

Action Plan for eService No.1

Model action plan for implementation.... (service name)

Problem: (problem description)				
General objective: (from Documents on strategic development of the locality, rayon, region, country)				
Goal: Implementing service (name) in LPA (locality)				
Activity/Sub-activity	Period	Responsible	Progress indicators	Monitoring Evaluation
	Start: End:		Product: Result:	
	Start: End:		Product: Result:	Intermediate: Ex-post:

Table: **Project Proposal Matrix**

PROJECT DESCRIPTION	INDICATORS	SOURCES OF VERIFICATION	ASSUMPTIONS
<p>Overall objective: The broad development impact to which the project contributes – at a national or sectoral level (provides the link to the policy and/or sector programme context)</p>	<p>Measures the extent to which a contribution to the overall objective has been made. Used during evaluation. However, it is often not appropriate for the project itself to try and collect this information.</p>	<p>Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently).</p>	
<p>Purpose: The development outcome at the end of the project – more specifically the expected benefits to the target group(s).</p>	<p>Helps answer the question “How will we know if the purpose has been achieved?” Should include appropriate details of quantity, quality and time.</p>	<p>Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently).</p>	<p>Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the purpose-objective linkage.</p>
<p>Results: The direct/tangible results (goods and services) that the project delivers, and which are largely under project management’s control.</p>	<p>Helps answer the question “How will we know if the results have been delivered?” Should include appropriate details of quantity, quality and time.</p>	<p>Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently).</p>	<p>Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the purpose-objective linkage.</p>
<p>Activities: The tasks (work programme) that need to be carried out to deliver the planned results</p>	<p>(sometimes a summary of resources /means is provided in this box)</p>	<p>(sometimes a summary of resources /means is provided in this box)</p>	<p>Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the purpose-objective linkage.</p>

7. Questionnaire for LPA from the Republic of Moldova

A short description:

Based on the findings of the seminar from November 24-25, problems stated by mayors and other local specialists, as well as presenters; Visegrad and Moldovan experts elaborated the following questionnaire for LPAs from Moldova. This questionnaire will help writing the action plan for LPA, mainly the chapter chapter: State of the Art (current situation).

Title: Questionnaire for Local Public Authorities (LPA) from the Republic of Moldova

The **goal** of this questionnaire is to determine the technical and personnel conditions for the design, implementation and operation of electronic services to the population at the local level.

Target group (or who should fulfil this questionnaire):

The Local Public Authorities representatives (cities, villages, state local district administration). A specialist of the LPA might write the document, but the mayor (signature, stamp) should approve it.

The received answers will be stored safely and used for preparation of better-focused projects that can help LPAs to create electronic services. Answers could also help LPA itself for development of plans for building electronic services.

A. Organisation – Contact data

1. Name of the LPA:
2. Level of LPA: I (city/village) or II (district-rayon)
3. General data (surface of the locality, the region, the general development level, socio-economic data)
4. Population in LPA:
5. Address:
6. Phone:
7. Fax:
8. Web page of LPA:
9. General/official e-mail:
10. Name, position in LPA of the person providing information:
11. Basic duties of the person providing information (please write 3-5 main job duties of your position in the LPA):
12. Direct phone to the person providing information:
13. E-mail address of the contact person:

B. Staff

1. Number of employees in general:
2. Number of IT staff:
3. Main duties of IT staff:

4. What kind of training was provided by LPA in last three years - name the courses in IT:
5. Are there any IT or communication services outsourced? If yes, which one?
6. Is there a written policy on data protection?
7. Is there a written policy on personal data protection?
8. Are the written procedures on IT maintenance?
9. Are there any written procedures on software copyright protection?
10. Are the any organizational certificates present (ISO 27001, ISO 9001, ISO 14000, ISO 20000, others)?
11. Any additional remarks to this section:

C. Infrastructure

1. How many PC do you have?
2. How many Laptops do you have?
3. How many MS Windows installations do you use (in PC)?
4. How many Linux installations do you use (in PC)?
5. How many physical servers are there?
6. How many virtual servers are there?
7. How many MS Windows installations are there (in servers)?
8. How many Linux installations are there (in servers)?
9. Do you use cloud storage for your data?
10. How many logical points are there in LAN?
11. How many routers are there?
12. How many firewalls are there? (SW or HW firewalls)
13. Is there an UTM device?
14. Are there any UPS devices?
15. How many laser printers are there?
16. How many scanners are there?
17. Who provides the internet services?
18. What is the speed of internet (upload/download)?
19. Any additional remarks to this section:

D. Software

1. Which office packet do you use (MS Office, Libre Office, ...)?
 2. Is there any accounting system? Which?
 3. Is there any human resources system? Which?
 4. Is there any local tax / fees system? Which?
 5. Is there any Document Management System? Which?
 6. Is there any Geographical Information System? Which?
 7. Is there any SQL database? Which and for which purposes?
-

8. Are there any other systems? Which?
9. Any additional remarks to this section:

E. Electronic Services (e-Services) situation

1. Do you have any e-Services in your LPA in operation? Which?
2. Do you plan to build e-Services? Which are in your priorities?
3. Do you have dedicated person responsible for conception of ICT/e-Services who also coordinates this process?
4. How you need to help with this subject?

Conclusions & Recommendations

The research study shows that LPAs in Moldova do not have any local development strategies. It is recommended to elaborate one, including a chapter concentrated on IT development. The topic is relatively new, so it is recommended to check how general guidelines on management apply to Moldova situation.

Proposed strategy should include:

1. Analysis of current state of IT – identification of problems
2. SWOT ->TOWS Strategic Analysis
3. IT Mission and Vision
4. Long-term, mid-term and short-term goals
5. KPI's of strategy and goals according to SMART principle
6. Proposed projects along with:
 - a. Goal
 - b. Scope
 - c. Budget
 - d. Timeline

It is also recommended for all LPAs to register as personal data holders at the National Center for Personal Data Protection, as well as to use the national domain name ".md" for developing official LPAs websites, to ensure information security.

Bibliography

Joint Integrated Local Development Programme, UNDP Moldova, available at http://www.md.undp.org/content/moldova/en/home/operations/projects/poverty_reduction/joint-integrated-local-development-programme.html

Study monitoring the web presence of localities from the Republic of Moldova, available in Romanian at <http://idsi.md/prezenta-web-a-localitatilor-din-Republica-Moldova>

What is an action plan? <http://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/structure/strategic-planning/develop-action-plans/main>

Legislation

Government Decision Nr. 188 of 03.04.2012 on the official webpages of the public administration authorities on the Internet

Law Nr. 133 of 08.07.2011 on personal data protection

Law on electronic communications nr. 241-XVI of 15.11.2007

Regulation on the management of top level domain names .md

Regulation on the the official webpages of the public administration authorities on the Internet

Online sources

<http://www.datepersonale.md/> - National Center for Personal Data Protection from Moldova

<http://www.registru.datepersonale.md> – Register of personal data holders

<http://www.anrceti.md/node/35> - National Regulatory Agency for Electronic Communications and Information Technology

<https://servicii.gov.md/> - National portal of e-services

www.cts.md – Center of Special Telecommunications

www.amp.gov.md – Aid Management Platform

<http://cancelaria.gov.md/> - State Chancellery of the Republic of Moldova

<http://www.ro-ua-md.net/> - Joint Operation Programme Romania – Republic of Moldova ENI 2014-2020

Annex 1. Seminar Agenda of the seminar**Agenda****Workshop: ICT-based Solutions for Local Services (Practical Aspects)****November 24 – 25, 2015 - Chisinau, Moldova****Labour Institute, Conference Hall – 1st level, 10 Zimbrului str., Chisinau, Moldova, 2024**

Day 1 – November 24		
Time	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.30 - 10.00	Arrival & registration	
	Welcome coffee	
10.00 - 10.10	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda	dr. Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.15- 10.25	Welcome speech	Acad. Ion Toghineanu , prime-vicepresident of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova
10.30 - 10.40	Welcome speech	Ceaus Sergiu , Deputy General Secretary of the Government
10.40 - 10.50	Welcome speech	Andrei Cusca , Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications
10.50-11.15	General and practical aspects regarding personal data protection	Sergiu Arsene, Sergiu Bozianu National Center for Personal Data Protection
11.15-11.40	Funding instruments for LPAs project from external sources	Victor Nicolaescu, Alexandru Rusu State Chancellery
11.40-12.15	Discussions & Coffee break * Common photo	
12.15- 13.05	Reusable government electronic services	Dumitru Postu, Sergiu Bedros E-Government Center
13.10-13.25	Participants introductions (First name/Last name, Locality, Position)	All participants
13.30-14.20	Lunch	
14.30-14.55	“.MD” domain for LPAs: penetrability, goals and reality	Dorian Bodiu , MoldData
15.00 - 15.25	IT instruments for LPAs	Olesea Cazacu , Project manager, Local Development and Migration Eugent Platita , IT consultant, Joint Integrated Program for Local Development

15.30-15.50	ICT solutions for LPAs (practical recommendations)	Vladimir Benko Expert from Slovakia
16.00 - 16.30	Discussions & Coffee break	
16.30-16.55	Some suggestions concerning local e-services to be developed	Vratislav Datel Expert from the Czech Republic
17.00-17.30	Novateca program	Maria Gonta, Novateca
17.30-17.50	TAP SYSTEM (example of outputs based on feedback questionnaires of Study Visit participants in Slovakia)	Vladimir Benko Expert from Slovakia
17.50 - 18.10	Final discussions & conclusions of the event	Anatol Gremalschi - IPP Ion Cosuleanu - IDSI
18.15 - 19.30	Dinner & Networking event	
Day 2 – November 25		
09.00 - 09.30	Study visit in Slovakia: good practices	Anastasia Stefanita, IDSI study visit participants
09.30-10.00	ISDI services – opportunities for LPAs	Igor Cojocar Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.00 - 10.20	Exemple of IT implementation program in LPA – I part	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert from Poland
10.20 - 10.45	Coffee break	
10.50-11.15	Exemple of IT implementation program in LPA – I part	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert from Poland
11.20- 11.50	Households Register. Conceptual approach	Mihai Grecu, Information Society Development Institute
11.50 - 12.30	Discussions: Electronic Households Register – necessary steps	Anatol Gremalschi, IPP Ion Cosuleanu, IDSI Mihai Grecu, IDSI
12.30 - 12.50	Seminar conclusions	
12.50 - 13.15	Handing participation certificates	
13.15 - 13.30	Feedback questionnaire	
	Final organisational issues	
13.30 - 15.00	Lunch	
15.00	Participants departure	

DISCUS is a project coordinated by the [Information Society Development Institute](#), with the support of partners from Visegrad countries and funded under the [International Visegrad Fund](#)

Annex 2: The 7th project factsheet – Seminar from November 24-25, 2015

<h1 style="margin: 0;">DISCUS</h1> <p style="margin: 0;">Seminar: ICT Solutions for Local Services (practical aspects)</p>	<p style="margin: 0;">24-25 november 2015 Chisinau</p>
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over **120**
participants

12
presentations

The seminar was attended by:

15 mayors

**20 deputy mayors,
secretaries of
local/district councils**

**20 representatives
of libraries,
schools/colleges/
universities**

The event was attended by:

- ✓ Acad. Ion Tighineanu, senior vice president of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova
- ✓ Sergiu Ceaus, Deputy Secretary General of the Government
- ✓ Andrei Cusca, Ministry of Information Technology and Communications
- ✓ Dr. Veaceslav Ursachi, head of the Engineering and Technology Sciences Department of ASM

3 Visegrad Experts

14 Local Experts

Annex 3. Personal data categories

Appendix No.1
to Requirements for the assurance of
personal data security at their
processing within the information
systems of personal data

CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA

1. Personal data which directly or indirectly identify a natural person, in particular, by reference to an identification number (personal code), to one or more specific elements of his physical, physiological, psychological, economic, cultural or social identity fall into two categories: common and special.

2. **Special category** of personal data is the information revealing racial or ethnic origin, political or religious beliefs, personal data concerning health or sexual life, as well as data relating to criminal conviction of a physic person.

3. **Common category** is the information that reveals:

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1) name and surname; | 17) banking data; |
| 2) gender; | 18) signature; |
| 3) date and place of birth; | 19) civil status data; |
| 4) citizenship; | 20) pension file number; |
| 5) IDNP; | 21) social security number (CPAS); |
| 6) image; | 22) medical insurance code (CPAM); |
| 7) voice; | 23) phone/fax number; |
| 8) family situation; | 24) cell phone number; |
| 9) military situation; | 25) address (domicile/residence); |
| 10) geographic location data/ traffic data; | 26) e-mail address; |
| 11) nickname/alias; | 27) genetic data; |
| 12) family members' personal data; | 28) biometric and anthropometric data; |
| 13) driving license data; | 29) finger print identification data; |
| 14) data from matriculation certificate; | 30) profession and/or work place; |
| 15) economic and financial situation; | 31) professional occupation - diploma - education; |
| 16) data of owned assets; | 32) habits/preferences/behaviors; |
| | 33) physical characteristics. |

4. In cases of common personal data processing, personal data holders will include in personal data security policy and will implement the requirements set up for the 1st security level of personal data information systems - (N-1).

5. In cases of special category of personal data processing, personal data holders, additionally to the set requirements for the 1st security level, will include in security policy of personal data and will implement requirements established for the 2nd security level of personal data information systems - (N-2).